

Approximate Solution of Slowly Varying Amplitude and Phase of Nonlinear Differential Systems Duffing Equation with External Forces

Rezaul Karim, Hasan Al Mamun, Pinakee Dey, Md. Nazmul Hossain, Md. Mijanoor1 Rahman, Md. Asaduzzaman, Saikh shahjahan Miah, Md. Shafiqul Islam

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 22, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : KBM Method, Damped Nonlinear System, Time Dependent Nonlinear Differential Systems, Forced Motion, Perturbation Methods, Approximate Solution and Struble's Technique</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6476692</p>	<p><i>Objectives: To present a new approximate solution to the field equations obtained nonlinear differential Systems by using duffing equation with external forces which yields constant varying parameter. Methods: To determine an approximate solution of nonlinear ordinary differential system with damping and slowly varying coefficients a damped oscillatory process is considered based on the Krylov-Bogoliubov (KB) method. This paper develops a reliable algorithm based on the general Struble's technique and extended KBM method for solving nonlinear differential systems. Moreover, we find a solution based on the KBM and general Struble's technique of nonlinear autonomous systems with vary slowly with time, which is more powerful than the existing perturbation method. The method is illustrated by an example. Findings: Our aimed to this paper of approximate Solution of Nonlinear Differential Systems duffing equation with external forces. However, in some cases it's feasible to alternate nonlinear differential equations with an associated linear equation closely enough to give helpful results. Novelty: By applying this method in an example, we find a solution by considering initial conditions. The figures explained the nonlinear phenomena for the critical situation. Finally, results are discussed, primarily to enrich the physical prospects, and shown graphically by utilizing MATHEMATICA and MATLAB software.</i></p>

Introduction

Generally, a significant approach, known as the expansion of the small parameter, is used to investigate nonlinear oscillatory systems, which is erected upon the perturbation theory. The perturbation theory can be defined as mathematical methods by which an approximate solution to a mathematical problem is figured out. Sharif et al^[1] presented for solving strongly nonlinear oscillators and Alam et al^[2] are extended generalization of the modified Lindstedt–Poincare method for solving some strong nonlinear oscillation. MAK et al.^[3] are developed new technique for obtaining approximate solution of higher order nonlinear differential equation. Karim et al^[4] be determined an approximate solution of nonlinear differential system with time variation. Anjum N and He JH^[5] are developed by homotopy perturbation method for N/MEMS oscillators and Dey et. al^[6] is obtained an asymptotic method for time dependent nonlinear systems with varying coefficient. MS, et al^[7] have been solving the quadratic nonlinear oscillator. Wagner UV and Lentz L^[8] has determined on the detection of artifacts in harmonic balancesolutions of nonlinear oscillators and Durur H, et al^[9] has found an approximate solutions of diffusion equations arising in oil pollution. It is periodic solutions of nonlinear differential equations by using a truncated Fourier series in which there exists a strongly nonlinear term based on the Harmonic balance (HB) method. In this paper, we have used combining the methods of extended Modified harmonic balance method . Usually, a set of strongly nonlinear algebraic equations appear among the unknown coefficients of several harmonic terms. Murty^[10] is find out the periodic solutions of second order nonlinear differential systems with small nonlinearities. Shortly after that, Hosen MA^[11] , Y ildirim A, et al^[12] has modified to damped oscillatory processes to the most well-known standard methods for constructing the approximate analytical solutions to the nonlinear oscillators are the perturbation techniques which harmonic balance method and energy balance method . For the first time, Krylov and Bogoliubov introduced a new perturbation method in order to discuss the transient state solution of the equation presented Shamsul Alam, M^[13], by

$$\ddot{x} + \omega^2 x = \epsilon F(x, \dot{x}) \quad (1.1)$$

where ϵ is a small parameter, ω is the angular frequency and \dot{x} is the derivative of x with respect to t and so on. But in particular cases, it gives those periodic solutions obtained by Poincare method is a well-known perturbation method for determining periodic solutions of nonlinear ordinary differential equations with small nonlinearities. When $\epsilon = 0$, then equation (1.1) reduce to linear equation and its solution is

$$x = a \cos(\omega t + \varphi) \quad (1.2)$$

where a and φ are arbitrary constant to be determined from the initial conditions. Now in order to determine an approximate solution of the equation (1.1) for ϵ small but different from zero, Krylov and Bogoliubov assumed that the solution is still given by (1.2) with the derivative of the from

$$\dot{x} = -a\omega \sin(t + \varphi) \quad (1.3)$$

Therefore, the first approximation solution of Krylov and Bogliubov method is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{a} = & -\frac{\epsilon}{2\pi\omega} \int_0^{2\pi} F(\cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \sin \psi d\psi \\ & -\frac{\epsilon}{2\pi a\omega} \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \cos \psi d\psi \end{aligned} \quad (1.4) \quad \dot{\varphi} =$$

where a and φ are independent of time under integrals. The equation (1.4) are the differential equations of the first approximation in the form in which they are originally, the method was developed by Krylov and Bogoliubov^[13] for obtaining periodic solution of a second order nonlinear differential equation. Ullah MW et al^[14] has modified harmonic balance method, He J-H and Latifizadeh H^[15] had investigated general numerical algorithm for nonlinear differential equations by the variational iteration method

The asymptotic method Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolskii (KBM) [1.1-1.3] is particularly convenient and extensively used methods to study nonlinear differential systems with small nonlinearities. This method, through it is restricted to differential equations of the type (1.1) has been extensively in plasma physics, theory of oscillations and control theory. Kruskal^[16] has extended this method to solve the equation of type

$$\ddot{x} = F(x, \dot{x}, \epsilon) \quad (1.5)$$

The solutions of these fully nonlinear equations are based on the recurrent relations and are given in the forms of power series of the small parameter ϵ . Cap⁽⁵⁾ has investigated some nonlinear systems of the type

$$\ddot{x} + \omega^2 f(x) = \epsilon F(x, \dot{x}) \quad (1.6)$$

They assumed the solution of the nonlinear differential equation(1.1) in the form

$$x = a \cos \psi + \epsilon u_1(a, \psi) + \epsilon^2 u_2(a, \psi) + \dots + \epsilon^n u_n(a, \psi) + o(\epsilon^{n+1}) \quad (1.7)$$

where $u_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are periodic functions of ψ with period 2π and a, b and ψ are function

of time t , defined by

$$\dot{a} = -\epsilon A_1(a) + \epsilon^2 A_2(a) \dots \dots + \epsilon^n A_n(a) + o(\epsilon^{n+1}) \quad (1.8)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = \omega + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a) \dots \dots + \epsilon^n B_n(a) + o(\epsilon^{n+1})$$

After replacing a and ψ by the function defined in equation (1.8), is a solution of (1.1). The function A_k and B_k generate the arbitrariness in the definitions of the functions u_k . To remove this arbitrariness, the following additional conditions are imposed.

$$\int_0^{2\pi} u_k(a, \psi) \cos \psi d\psi = 0,$$

(1.9)

$$\int_0^{2\pi} u_k(a, \psi) \sin \psi \, d\psi = 0,$$

These conditions guarantee the absence of secular terms in all successive. These conditions guarantee the absence of secular terms in all successive approximations. Dey et al.^[6] extended the technique for damped forced nonlinear systems with varying coefficients. Nonlinear oscillatory systems such as those governed by

$$\ddot{x} + \omega^2 x = \epsilon F(x, \dot{x}, t) \quad (1.10)$$

He expressed the asymptotic solution of this equation for small ϵ in the form

$x = a \cos(\omega t - \theta) + \sum_{n=1}^N \epsilon^n x_n(t) + O(\epsilon^{N+1})$ where a and θ are slowly varying functions of time. In other recent papers, a simple technique Ganji DD. et al [17] has presented to determine an analytical solution of nonlinear differential equations two oscillators mechanism using Akbari–Ganji method. The aim of this article is a new approximate solution to the field equations obtained nonlinear differential Systems by using duffing equation with external forces which yields constant varying parameter and also obtained approximate solution by graphically.

2. Method and Materials

We consider the Krylov-Bogoliubov first approximation to the solution of differential equations having the form

$$\ddot{y} + y = \epsilon F(y, \dot{y}), \quad 0 < \epsilon \ll 1 \quad (2.1)$$

We seek a solution of equation (2.1) in the form

$$y = a \cos \psi + \epsilon u_1(a, \psi) + \epsilon^2 u_2(a, \psi) + \dots \quad (2.2)$$

Where $u_1(a, \psi)$, $u_2(a, \psi)$, ... are periodic functions of ψ with a period 2π , and the quantities a and ψ are functions of time defined by the following differential equations:

$$\dot{a} = \epsilon A_1(a) + \epsilon^2 A_2(a) + \dots \quad (2.3)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a) + \dots$$

The functions $u_1(a, \psi)$, $u_2(a, \psi)$, ... , $A_1(a)$, $A_2(a)$, ... and $B_1(a)$, $B_2(a)$, ... are to be chosen in such a way that equation (2.2) after replacing a and ψ by the functions defined in equations (2.3), is a solution of equation (2.1). Thus if, $A_1(a)$, $A_2(a)$, ... and $B_1(a)$, $B_2(a)$, ... are polynomial functions of a . Then the integration of equations (2.3) may be done using well-known techniques of calculus.

If we limit to a finite number of terms, equations (2.2) and (2.3) become

$$y = a \cos \psi + \epsilon u_1(a, \psi) + \dots + \epsilon^m u_m(a, \psi) \quad (2.4)$$

$$\dot{a} = \epsilon A_1(a) + \epsilon^2 A_2(a) + \dots + \epsilon^m A_m(a) \quad (2.5)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a) + \dots + \epsilon^m B_m(a)$$

where $m=1, 2, \dots$

The practical applicability of this technique is not determined by the convergence (or non-convergence) of the series given by equations (2.4) and (2.5) when $m \rightarrow \infty$, but by their asymptotic properties for a given fixed value of m when $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. Thus equations (2.2) and (2.3) will be treated as formal expansions necessary for obtaining the asymptotic approximation given by equations (2.4) and (2.5).

It can be easily shown that there is an arbitrariness in the definition of the functions $u_1(a, \psi)$. Since there are no restrictions in choosing the functions $A_k(a)$ and $B_k(a)$ that generate the functions $u_1(a, \psi)$. To remove this arbitrariness, the following additional conditions are imposed:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} u_i(a, \psi) \sin \psi \, d\psi = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \dots \dots \quad (2.6)$$

$$\int_0^{2\pi} u_i(a, \psi) \cos \psi \, d\psi = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots \dots \dots$$

The conditions given in equations (2.6) eliminate the fundamental harmonic in the functions $u_i(a, \psi)$ and, in addition, guarantee the absence of secular terms in all successive approximations.

We now give the procedure for determining the functions $u_i(a, \psi)$, $A_i(a)$, and $B_i(a)$.

Let $F(a, \psi)$ be a function of the variables a and ψ . The first and second derivatives of $F(a, \psi)$, with respect to time t , are

$$\frac{dF(a, \psi)}{dt} = \frac{da}{dt} \frac{\partial F}{\partial a} + \frac{d\psi}{dt} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \psi} \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$\frac{d^2 F(a, \psi)}{dt^2} = \frac{d^2 a}{dt^2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial a} + \frac{d^2 \psi}{dt^2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \psi} + \left(\frac{da}{dt}\right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial a^2} + 2 \frac{da}{dt} \frac{d\psi}{dt} \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial a \partial \psi} + \left(\frac{d\psi}{dt}\right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial \psi^2} \quad (2.8)$$

Thus the first and second derivatives of the function y are

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = \frac{da}{dt} \left(\cos \psi + \epsilon \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial a} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial a} - \dots \right) + \frac{d\psi}{dt} \left(-a \sin \psi - \epsilon \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \psi} + \dots \right) \quad (2.9)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} = & \frac{d^2 a}{dt^2} \left(\cos \psi + \epsilon \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial a} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial a} + \dots \right) - \frac{d^2 \psi}{dt^2} \left(-a \sin \psi + \epsilon \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \psi} + \dots \right) + \left(\frac{da}{dt}\right)^2 \left(\epsilon \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial a^2} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial a^2} + \dots \right) \\ & + 2 \frac{da}{dt} \frac{d\psi}{dt} \left(-\sin \psi + \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial a \partial \psi} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial a \partial \psi} + \dots \right) + \left(\frac{d\psi}{dt}\right)^2 \left(-a \cos \psi + \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \psi^2} + \epsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial \psi^2} + \dots \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Using equations 2.5, we obtain the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d^2 a}{dt^2} &= \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right) = \frac{da}{dt} \frac{d}{da} \left(\frac{da}{dt} \right) = \frac{da}{dt} \sum_{n=1}^m \epsilon^n \frac{dA_n}{da} \\ &= \epsilon^2 A_1 \frac{dA_1}{da} + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d^2 \psi}{dt^2} &= \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{d\psi}{dt} \right) = \frac{da}{dt} \frac{d}{da} \left(\frac{d\psi}{dt} \right) = \frac{da}{dt} \sum_{n=1}^m \epsilon^n \frac{dB_n}{da} \\ &= \epsilon^2 A_1 \frac{dB_1}{da} + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.12)$$

$$\left(\frac{da}{dt} \right)^2 = (\epsilon A_1 + \epsilon^2 A_2 + \dots)^2 = \epsilon^2 A_1^2 - O(\epsilon^3) \quad (2.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{da}{dt} \frac{d\psi}{dt} &= (\epsilon A_1 + \epsilon^2 A_2 + \dots)(1 + \epsilon B_1 + \epsilon^2 B_2 + \dots) \\ &= \epsilon A_1 + \epsilon^2 (A_2 + A_1 B_1) + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\left(\frac{d\psi}{dt} \right)^2 &= (1 + \epsilon B_1 + \epsilon^2 B_2 + \dots)^2 \\ &= 1 + 2\epsilon B_1 + \epsilon^2 (B_1^2 + 2B_2) + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.15)$$

If we substitute equations (2.11) to (2.15) into equations (2.9) and (2.10) and place terms of the same power of ϵ together, we obtain

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = -a \sin \psi + \epsilon \left(A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi} \right) + \epsilon^2 \left(A_2 \cos \psi - a B_2 \sin \psi + A_1 \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial a} + B_1 \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi} + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \psi} \right) + O(\epsilon^3) \quad (2.16)$$

And

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} &= -a \cos \psi + \epsilon \left(-2A_1 \sin \psi - 2aB_1 \cos \psi + \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \psi^2} \right) + \epsilon^2 \left[\left(A_1 \frac{dA_1}{da} - aB_1^2 - 2aB_2 \right) \cos \psi - \left(2A_2 + 2A_1 B_1 + A_1 \frac{dB_1}{da} a \right) \sin \psi + 2A_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial a \partial \psi} + 2B_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \psi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial \psi^2} \right] + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.17)$$

Hence the L.H.S. of equation (2.1) may be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} + y &= \epsilon \left(-2A_1 \sin \psi - 2aB_1 \cos \psi + \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \psi^2} + u_1 \right) + \epsilon^2 \left[\left(A_1 \frac{dA_1}{da} - aB_1^2 - 2aB_2 \right) \cos \psi - \left(2A_2 + 2A_1 B_1 + A_1 \frac{dB_1}{da} a \right) \sin \psi + 2A_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial a \partial \psi} + 2B_1 \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial \psi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial \psi^2} - u_2 \right] + O(\epsilon^3)\end{aligned}\quad (2.18)$$

Also, the R.H.S. of equation (2.1) may be written in the following form:

$$\epsilon F \left(y, \frac{dy}{dt} \right) = \epsilon F \left(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi \right) + \epsilon^2 \left[u_1(a, \psi) F_y \left(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi \right) + \left(A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi} \right) F_y \left(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi \right) \right] + O(\epsilon^3) \quad (2.19)$$

Where we use the following notation:

$$h_1(a) + 2A_1 = 0$$

Thus

$$u_1(a, \psi) = g_0(a) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left[\frac{g_n(a) \cos n\psi + h_n(a) \sin n\psi}{1-n^2} \right] \quad (2.27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= -\frac{h_1(a)}{2} \\ &= -\left(\frac{1}{2\pi}\right) \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \sin \psi \, d\psi \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 &= -\frac{g_1(a)}{2a} \\ &= -\left(\frac{1}{2\pi a}\right) \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \cos \psi \, d\psi \end{aligned} \quad (2.29) \text{ where}$$

$$g_n(a) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \cos n\psi \, d\psi \quad (2.30)$$

$$h_n(a) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \sin n\psi \, d\psi$$

Since $u_1(a, \psi)$, $A_1(a)$, and $B_1(a)$ have been determined, we may calculate $F_1(a, \psi)$ from equation (2.22). Expanding $F_1(a, \psi)$ in a Fourier series gives

$$F_1(a, \psi) = g_0^{(1)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [g_n^{(1)}(a) \cos n\psi + h_n^{(1)}(a) \sin n\psi] \quad (2.31)$$

Likewise, expanding $u_2(a, \psi)$ in a Fourier series, substituting it and equation (2.31) into the second of equations (2.21) and imposing the condition given by equation (2.6) gives

$$\begin{aligned} A_2 &= -\frac{h_1^{(1)}(a)}{2} \\ B_2 &= -\frac{g_1^{(1)}(a)}{2a} \end{aligned} \quad (2.32)$$

$$u_2(a, \psi) = g_0^{(1)}(a) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left[\frac{g_n^{(1)}(a) \cos n\psi + h_n^{(1)}(a) \sin n\psi}{1-n^2} \right]$$

From equation (2.22) and the definition of Fourier coefficients, we obtain the following results for $A_2(a)$ and $B_2(a)$:

$$A_2(a) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(2A_1 B_1 + A_1 \frac{dB_1}{da} a \right) - \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} \left[[u_1(a, \psi) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi)] + (A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi}) F_y'(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \right] \sin \psi \, d\psi \quad (2.33)$$

$$B_2(a) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(B_1^2 - \left(\frac{A_1}{a} \right) \frac{dA_1}{da} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{2\pi a} \right) \int_0^{2\pi} \left[[u_1(a, \psi) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi)] + (A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \psi}) F_y'(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \right] \cos \psi \, d\psi \quad (2.34)$$

The evaluation of the higher approximation should be sufficiently clear. Note that the method previously described permits us to evaluate $u_i(a, \psi)$, $A_i(a)$, and $B_i(a)$ up to any value of i . Thus we may construct approximate solutions satisfying equations (2.1) correct to any order in ϵ .

The first approximation to the solution of equation (2.1), according to the Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolsky asymptotic method is

$$y = a \cos \psi$$

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \epsilon A_1(a) \quad (2.35)$$

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a)$$

Note that this is the same as the first approximation of Krylov and Bogoliubov. Likewise, the second approximation is

$$y = a \cos \psi + \epsilon u_1(a, \psi)$$

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \epsilon A_1(a) + \epsilon^2 A_2(a) \quad (2.36)$$

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a)$$

In general, the n th order approximation is given by the following system of equations:

$$y = a \cos \psi + \epsilon u_1(a, \psi) + \dots + \epsilon^{n-1} u_{n-1}(a, \psi)$$

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \epsilon A_1(a) + \epsilon^2 A_2(a) + \dots + \epsilon^n A_n(a) \quad (2.36)$$

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a) + \dots + \epsilon^n B_n(a)$$

2.2.1 Example

Consider the un-damped nonlinear oscillator

$$\ddot{y} + y + \epsilon y^2 = 0, F = -y^2 \quad (2.37)$$

where $F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) = -a^2 \cos^2 \psi$

$$= -\frac{a^2}{2} \cdot 2 \cos^2 \psi$$

$$= -\left(\frac{a^2}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{a^2}{2}\right) \cos 2\psi$$

and the corresponding Fourier coefficients are

$$g_0(a) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos^2 \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \left[\psi + \frac{\sin 2\psi}{2} \right]_0^{2\pi}$$

$$= -a^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} g_1(a) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^3 \psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{4} [\cos 3\psi + 3 \cos \psi] \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{4\pi} \left[\frac{\sin 3\psi}{3} + 3 \sin \psi \right]_0^{2\pi} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} g_2(a) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \cos 2\psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos^2 \psi \cos 2\psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (1 + \cos 2\psi) \cos 2\psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\cos 2\psi + \cos^2 2\psi) \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left\{ \cos 2\psi + \frac{1}{2}(1 + \cos 4\psi) \right\} \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \left[\frac{\sin 2\psi}{2} + \frac{\psi}{2} + \frac{\sin 4\psi}{8} \right]_0^{2\pi} \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$g_i(a) = 0, \quad i = 3, 4, 5, \dots$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned} h_n &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \sin n\psi \, d\psi \\ h_0 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \cdot 0 \, d\psi = 0 \\ h_1 &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (1 + \cos 2\psi) \sin \psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\sin \psi + \cos 2\psi \sin \psi) \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \sin \psi \, d\psi - \frac{a^2}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} 2 \cos 2\psi \sin \psi \, d\psi \\ &= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi} [-\cos \psi]_0^{2\pi} - \frac{a^2}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (\sin 3\psi - \sin \psi) \, d\psi \end{aligned}$$

$$= -\frac{a^2}{2\pi}(-1+1) - \frac{a^2}{4\pi}[-\cos\psi/3 + \cos\psi]_0^{2\pi}$$

$$= 0$$

$$h_n(a) = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \dots \dots$$

Hence $U_1(a, \psi) = g_0(a) + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [g_n(a) \cos n\psi + h_n(a) \sin n\psi] / (1 - n^2)$

$$= -a^2 + \frac{-a^2 \cos 2\psi/2}{1-2^2}$$

$$= -a^2 + \frac{a^2 \cos 2\psi}{6}$$

$$A_1 = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} F(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \sin \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= 0$$

$$B_1 = -\frac{1}{2\pi a} \int_0^{2\pi} -a^2 \cos^2 \psi \cos \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= \frac{a}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \cos^3 \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= \frac{a}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{4} (\cos 3\psi + 3 \cos \psi) \, d\psi$$

$$= \frac{a}{8\pi} \left[\frac{\sin 3\psi}{3} + 3 \sin \psi \right]_0^{2\pi}$$

$$= 0$$

$$A_2(a) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(2A_1 B_1 + A_1 \frac{dB_1}{da} a \right) - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[U_1(a, \psi) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) + \right. \quad \left. (A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial \psi}) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \right] \sin \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= 0 - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[\left(-a^2 + \frac{a^2}{6} \cos \psi \right) (-a^2 \cos^2 \psi) + 0 \right] \sin \psi \, d\psi$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left(a^4 \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi - \frac{a^4}{6} \cos 2\psi \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi \right) \, d\psi$$

$$= \frac{a^4}{12\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} (2 \cos^4 \psi \sin \psi - \cos^2 \psi \sin \psi) \, d\psi$$

$$= 0$$

Similarly, $B_2(a) = -\frac{1}{2} \left[B_1^2 - \frac{A_1}{a} \frac{dA_1}{da} \right] - \frac{1}{2\pi a} \int_0^{2\pi} \left[U_1(a, \psi) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) + (A_1 \cos \psi - a B_1 \sin \psi + \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial \psi}) F_y(a \cos \psi, -a \sin \psi) \right] \cos \psi \, d\psi$

$$= -\frac{5a^2}{12}$$

Thus, in second approximation, we have

$$y = a \cos \psi + \epsilon U_1(a, \psi) \quad (2.38)$$

$$= a \cos \psi + \epsilon \left[\frac{a^2}{6} \cos 2\psi - a^2 \right]$$

$$\frac{da}{dt} = \epsilon A_1 = 0 \Rightarrow a = A_0$$

$$\frac{d\psi}{dt} = 1 + \epsilon B_1(a) + \epsilon^2 B_2(a)$$

$$= 1 + 0 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 a^2}{12}$$

$$= 1 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 a^2}{12}$$

$$d\psi = \left(1 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 a^2}{12}\right) dt$$

$$\therefore \psi = \left(1 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 a^2}{12}\right) t + \psi_0$$

Substituting the values in equation (2.38), we get

$$y = A_0 \cos \left[\left(1 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 A_0^2}{12}\right) t + \psi_0 \right] + \epsilon \left(\frac{A_0^2}{6} \right) \left\{ \cos \left[2 \left(1 - \frac{5\epsilon^2 A_0^2}{12}\right) t + 2\psi_0 \right] - 6 \right\}$$

where A_0 and ψ_0 are constants.

Figure-2.2.1(a): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions [$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.1$]

Figure-2.2.1(b)

Figure-2.2.1(b): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions $y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.2$

Figure-2.2.1(c)

Figure-2.2.1(c): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions $[y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.3]$

Figure-2.2.1(d)

Figure-2.2.1(d): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions [$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.4$]

Figure-2.2.1(e)

Figure-2.2.1(e): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions [$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.45$]

Figure-2.2.1(f)

Figure-2.2.1(f): Un-damped Non-linear oscillation with corresponding numerical solution is plotted with initial conditions [$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0, \epsilon = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.45$]

2.4. Duffing equation with external forces with example

Let us consider the *Duffing* equation with external forces

$$\ddot{x} + \omega_0^2 x = -\epsilon x^3 + \epsilon F \cos mt \quad (4.8)$$

where m is the frequency of the external forces. When $\epsilon = 0$ equation (4.9) has two eigenvalues $\mu_1 = i\omega$ and $\mu_2 = -i\omega$

Thus for equation (4.8), we obtain

$$f^{(0)} = -\{a_1^3 e^{3\mu_1 t} + 3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(2\mu_1 + \mu_2)t} + 3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(\mu_1 + 2\mu_2)t} + a_2^3 e^{3\mu_2 t} - \frac{F}{2}(e^{imt} + e^{-imt}) + 3\epsilon(a_1 e^{t\mu_1} + a_2 e^{t\mu_2})^2 \mu_1 + \dots \quad (4.9)$$

Therefore, equation (4.6) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & e^{\mu_1 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mu_1 - \mu_2 \right) (\epsilon A_1 + \dots) + e^{\mu_2 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mu_1 - \mu_2 \right) (\epsilon A_2 + \dots) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \mu_1 \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \mu_2 \right) (\epsilon u_1 + \dots) \\ & = -\epsilon \left\{ -\{a_1^3 e^{3\mu_1 t} + 3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(2\mu_1 + \mu_2)t} + 3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(\mu_1 + 2\mu_2)t} + a_2^3 e^{3\mu_2 t} - \frac{F}{2}(e^{imt} + e^{-imt}) + 3\epsilon(a_1 e^{t\mu_1} + a_2 e^{t\mu_2})^2 \mu_1 + \dots \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Following the assumption (discussed in section 2) u_1 excludes the terms $3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(2\mu_1 + \mu_2)t}$, $3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(\mu_1 + 2\mu_2)t}$ and $\epsilon F(e^{imt} + e^{-imt})$. Thus, for equation (4.10), we obtain

$$e^{\lambda_1 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \right) A_1 = -3 a_1^2 a_2 e^{(2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)t} + E e^{i\nu t} / 2 \quad (4.11)$$

$$e^{\lambda_2 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \lambda_2 - \lambda_1 \right) A_2 = -3a_1 a_2^2 e^{(\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2)t} + E e^{-i\nu t} / 2 \quad (4.12)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_1 \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_2 \right) u_1 = - \left(a_1^3 e^{3\lambda_1 t} + a_2^3 e^{3\lambda_2 t} \right). \quad (4.13)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & e^{\lambda_1 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \right) B_1 + e^{\lambda_2 t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 \right) B_2 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_1 \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_2 \right) u_2 \\ &= -3(a_1^2 e^{2\lambda_1 t} + 2a_1 a_2 e^{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)t} + a_2^2 e^{2\lambda_2 t}) u_1 - \left(A_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_1} + A_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_2} \right) (A_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} + A_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}) \\ & - \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_1 \right) \left(A_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_1} + A_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_2} \right) u_1 - \left(A_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_1} + A_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial a_2} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \lambda_2 \right) u_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

Solving Equ. (4.11)-(4.13), we obtain

$$A_1 = \frac{-3a_1^2 a_2 e^{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)t}}{2\lambda_1} + \frac{E e^{(i\nu - \lambda_1)t}}{2(i\nu - \lambda_2)} \quad (4.15)$$

$$A_2 = \frac{-3a_1 a_2^2 e^{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)t}}{2\lambda_2} + \frac{-E e^{-(i\nu + \lambda_2)t}}{2(i\nu + \lambda_1)} \quad (4.16)$$

and

$$u_1 = \frac{-a_1^3 e^{3\lambda_1 t}}{2\lambda_1(3\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} + \frac{-a_2^3 e^{3\lambda_2 t}}{2\lambda_2(3\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)} \quad (4.17)$$

Now, using the variables $a_1 = a e^{i\phi} / 2$, $a_2 = a e^{-i\phi} / 2$ and the eigenvalues by $\lambda_1 = i\omega$, $\lambda_2 = -i\omega$ and simplifying, we obtain the variational equations for a and ϕ in the real form (a and ϕ are known as amplitude and phase). Therefore, the equation (4.15) transform to

$$\dot{a} = \varepsilon E p_1 \sin \psi \quad (4.18)$$

and

$$\dot{\phi} = (\omega - \nu) + \varepsilon q_1 a^2 + \varepsilon E p_1 \cos \psi / a \quad (4.19)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &= -1/(\omega + \nu), \\ q_1 &= 3/8\omega, \end{aligned}$$

The form of the variational equations (4.18) and (4.19) are same as the form of the KBM solution. The variational equations for amplitude and phases are usually appeared in a set of first order differential equations and solved by a numerical technique.

Therefore, the improved solution of the equation (4.8) is

$$x(t, \varepsilon) = a \cos \varphi + \varepsilon u_1 + \dots,$$

Figure 2: Perturbation solution (with KBM and HB method) (dotted line) with corresponding numerical solution (solid line) are plotted with initial conditions $[x(0) = 1.0000, \dot{x}(0) = 0]$ or $a = 1.00000, \varphi = 0.0000$ for $\varepsilon = .6, E = .5, \nu = 1, \omega = 1$.

Figure-3: Perturbation solution (dotted line) with corresponding numerical solution (solid line) are plotted with initial conditions $[x(0) = 1., \dot{x}(0) = 0.0]$ or $[a = 1., \varphi = 0.0]$ for $\varepsilon = 1, \omega = \omega_0 \sqrt{(\zeta_1^2 + \zeta_2 \cos \tau)}$,

Results and discussions:

Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolskii method is modified and applied to certain damped nonlinear systems with slowly varying amplitude and phase. It represents the relationship between a continuously varying quantity and its rate of change. An asymptotic series itself is not convergent, but for a fixed number of terms the approximate solution tends to the exact solution as t tends to zero. Finally KBM method is used to determine the stationary amplitudes and their stabilities. Thus a and φ are slowly varying function of time because ε is small; hence they change is very little during the time $T = 2\pi$. The method is illustrated by the examples. For specified values of the parameters φ , k and the initial conditions are calculated. It can be easily shown that the static solution $y \equiv 0$ is un-stable. Thus, no matter how small A_0 is chosen, the amplitude will monotonically increase and approach, asymptotically in time, the value $a = 2$. On the other hand, if the initial amplitude is greater than two in value (i.e., $A > 2$), then the amplitude will monotonically decrease and approach, asymptotically in time, the value $a = 2$. For those initial conditions, the first approximate solutions are plotted along of that equation in 2.2.1(e) -2.2.1(f). A technique is presented based on the KBM method and general Struble's technique to determine approximate solutions of nonlinear differential systems which vary with time. In order to test the accuracy of an approximate solution obtained by a certain perturbation method, one compares the approximate solution to the numerical solution (considered to be exact). With regard to such a comparison concerning the presented Struble's technique of this article, we refer to the works of Murty^[1], Shamsul^[2,14] and Pinakee *et al*^[6] and Karim *et al*^[4]. In our present paper, for different initial conditions, we have compared the perturbation solutions (4.18) of Duffing's equations (4.7) to those obtained by Runge-Kutta fourth-order procedure. First of all, x is calculated by (4.18) with initial conditions $[x(0) = 1., \dot{x}(0) = 0.0]$ or $[a = 1., \varphi = 0.0]$ for $\varepsilon = 1, \omega = \omega_0 \sqrt{(\zeta_1^2 + \zeta_2 \cos \tau)}$. Then corresponding numerical solutions is also computed by Runge-Kutta fourth-order method. The result is shown in Fig.1-3. We see that in Fig.-2 the perturbation solution nicely agree with the numerical solution, but in this situation existing perturbation solution (unified method) in Fig.-3 does not agree.

Conclusion

In this paper, a modified form of harmonic balance method and perturbation method has been presented to approximate solution of nonlinear differential systems duffing equation with external forces. The method is simpler than the classical method and measure better result for strong nonlinearities. The method can be preceded to higher order nonlinear systems.

Conflict Of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to the publication of this article.

References

- Nazmul Sharif, Abdur Razzak & M. Z. Alam (2019) Modified harmonic balance method for solving strongly nonlinear oscillators, *Journal of Interdisciplinary Mathematics*, 22:3, 353375, DOI: 10.1080/09720502.2019.1624304
- Alam MS, Yeasmin IA and Ahamed MS. Generalization of the modified Lindstedt–Poincare method for solving some strong nonlinear oscillators. *Ain Shams Eng J* 2019; 10: 195–201.
- Azad MAK, Rahman MS, Molla MHU. A new technique for obtaining approximate solution of higher order nonlinear differential equation. *J interdisciplinary Mathematics* 2019; DOI: 10.1080/09720502.2019.1675291.
- Karim, R., Dey, P., & Miah, S. (2021). Approximate solution of nonlinear differential system with time variation. *Journal of Bangladesh Academy of Sciences*, 44(2), 121-130. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jbas.v44i2.51456>.
- Anjum N and He JH. Homotopy perturbation method for N/MEMS oscillators. *Math Meth Appl Sci*. 2020; 1–15, doi.org/ 10.1002/mma.6583
- Dey P, Ali MZ, Alam MS and Roy KC. An asymptotic method for time dependent nonlinear systems with varying coefficient, *J. Mech. Cont. Math. Sci*. 2008; 3(2): 354-370.
- Yeasmin IA, Sharif MN, Rahman MS, et al. Analytical technique for solving the quadratic nonlinear oscillator. *Results Phys* 2020
- Wagner UV and Lentz L. On the detection of artifacts in harmonic balance solutions of nonlinear oscillators. *Appl Math Modell* 2019; 65: 408–414.
- Ahmad H, Khan TA, Durur H, et al. Analytical approximate solutions of diffusion equations arising in oil pollution. *J. Ocean Eng. Sci* 2021 30(11): 4797–4810. doi:10.1016/j.joes.2020.05.002.
- Murty ISN. A unified Krylov-Bogoliubov method for solving second order nonlinear systems, *Int. J. Nonlinear Mech.* 1971; 6: 45-53
- Hosen MA, Chowdhury MSH, Ismail GM and Yildirim A. A modified harmonic balance method to obtain higher-order approximations to strongly nonlinear oscillators. *J Interdiscip Math* 2020; 23(7): 1325–1345.
- Alal Hosen Md, Ismail GM, Yildirim A, et al. A modified energy balance method to obtain higher-order analytical approximations to the oscillators with cubic and harmonic restoring force. *J App Comp Mech* 2020; 6(2): 320–331.
- Shamsul Alam, M., A unified Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolskii method for solving -th order nonlinear systems, *J. Frank .Inst.* Vol.339,pp. 239-248,2002..
- Ullah MW, Rahman MS, Uddin MA. A modified harmonic balance method for solving forced vibration problems with strong nonlinearity. *Journal of Low Frequency Noise, Vibration and Active Control* 2020; DOI: 10.1177/1461348420923433
- He J-H and Latifizadeh H. A general numerical algorithm for nonlinear differential equations by the variational iteration method. *Int J Numer Methods Heat Fluid Flow* 2020; 30(11): 4797–4810
- Kruskal M. Asymptotic theory of Hamiltonian and other systems with all situationsnearlyperiodic.*J. Math.Phys.* 1962; 3: 806-828.
- Hosseinzadeh S, Hosseinzadeh K, Rahai M, Ganji DD. Analytical solution of nonlinear differential equations two oscillators mechanism using Akbari–Ganji method. *Modern Physics Letters B*. 2021 Nov 10;35(31):2150462. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217984921504625>

Author Information

Rezaul Karim

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Hasan Al Mamun

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Pinakee Dey

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Md. Mijanoor

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Md. Asaduzzaman

Department of CSE, Ranada Prasad Shaha
University, Narayanganj, Bangladesh

Md. Shafiqul Islam

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Md. Nazmul Hossain

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Bangamata Sheikh Fojilatunnesa Mujib Science and
Technology University, Jamalpur-2012, Bangladesh

Rahman

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University

Saikh shahjahan Miah

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science,
Mawlana Bhashani Science and Technology
University
